

swarmchestrator

Application-level Swarm-based Orchestration Across the
Cloud-to-Edge Continuum

D8.1-Project Quality Handbook

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Glossary

ABBREVIATION	DEFINTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
DPO	Data Protection Office
EAC	Ethical Advisory Committee
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
PM	Project Manager
PMB	Project Management Board
PrC	Project Coordinator
TMB	Technical Management Board
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This Project Quality Handbook identifies and enumerates the tools chosen by the project in order to maximize the distribution of the information internally (and partly externally) in the project, and to enhance internal communication, to inform the project members and EC about the status of the ongoing work, to monitor and manage the project efficiently, and smoothly to achieve the objectives laid down in the Description of the Action.

This is meant to be a public deliverable, yet it is a living document that will be continuously updated throughout the project's lifetime.

Introduction

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the administrative, financial, and technical management procedures, and define the relevant structures and quality assurance processes that will support the execution of the project. The provisions contained therein are consistent with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

D8.1 details the project management structure and introduces the management bodies, the entities and players that ensure the successful completion of the project. In the upcoming section the general rules and procedures that define the implementation of the project are explained. The third section outlines the means and scheduling of project reporting, while the last section lists all the tools that enable swift and smooth collaboration between the Swarmchestrator partners.

1. Project management structure and management bodies

1.1. General management structure

In order to ensure seamless and successful implementation of the project the management structure of the Consortium will comprise the following entities:

- **Project Management Board (PMB)** acting as the decision-making body of the Consortium that globally supervises the overall project.
- **Technical Management Board (TMB)** shall be the supervisory body for the execution of the Project that reports and is accountable to the PMB. The TMB ensures the realization of the objectives described in each respective Work Package (WP)

The activities of these boards will be supported by the following players:

- **Project Coordinator (PrC)** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Beneficiaries and Associated Partners (further Parties) and the Granting Authority. PrC Coordinator, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, performs the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA).
- **Project Manager (PM)** assists the PMB, and the Project Coordinator.
- **Work Package Leader (WPL)** ensures the realization of the objectives described in each respective Work Package (WP).

1.2. Entities and players within the management structure

1.2.1. Project Management Board (PMB)

The PMB consists of two representatives of the Coordinator and one representative of each other Parties (Project Management Board Member). An additional representative of the Coordinator may participate at the meetings without voting rights. Associated Partners are excluded from voting on and vetoing regarding certain decisions of the PMB. Only the votes of Members with voting rights regarding the item in question will be counted. The PM shall chair all meetings of the Project Management Board, unless decided otherwise.

The Parties agree to abide by all decisions of the PMB. This does not prevent the Parties from exercising their veto rights, or from submitting a dispute to resolution in accordance with the provisions of this CA.

1.2.2. Technical Management Board (TMB)

The TMB consists of the Project Coordinator, Project Manager, and the WP Leaders. It is responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the PMB. The PM shall chair all meetings of the Technical Management Board, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds (2/3). The PMB is informed by decisions taken at the TMB via the Coordinator.

1.2.3. Ethical Advisory Committee (EAC)

The Ethical Advisory Committee will monitor and assess ethic compliance throughout the project. The details regarding EAC will be defined in D8.2- Data Management Plan and Ethical Monitoring Processes due in M6.

1.2.4. Project Coordinator (PrC)

PrC will be the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator will be responsible for performing all tasks and achieving all objectives described in the Grant Agreement (GA). Mr. Robert Lovas from SZTAKI is the Project Coordinator. He has been nominated as PrC considering his extensive experience in coordinating of Research and Innovation projects. The PrC is the single point of contact between the EC and the Consortium and oversees the contractual obligations. If required, the Project Coordinator organises meetings of the PMB for decision-making. However, it shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party. The overall tasks and functions are pursuant to the GA and WP8 description and include overall management of the project with the support of the TMB, the PM and WP Leaders.

If the Project Coordinator fails in its coordination tasks, the PMB may propose to the Granting Authority to change PrC. The Project Coordinator shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party or of the Consortium, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the GA or this CA. The PrC shall not enlarge its role beyond the tasks specified in CA and in GA.

Before sending any proposal for amendment to the GA on behalf of the Parties, the Project Coordinator will present the documents in question to the Parties and receive their explicit acceptance, which shall not be unreasonably withheld and shall be given within a reasonable time specified by the PrC. The terms and conditions of the amendment shall only be binding for the Parties if the majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the Parties have given their prior explicit acceptance in writing.

1.2.5. Project Manager (PM)

The PM assists the PMB and the Coordinator and is leading the technical implementation and research work in the project. The PM provides quality check for the deliverables and defines the agenda for the project events and chairs the TMB and the PMB. Based on his extensive experience in leading similar projects Mr. Tamás Kiss from UoW is fulfilling the role of the PM.

1.2.6. Work Package Leader (WPL)

PMB appointed for each Work Package a Work Package Leader (WPL) to coordinate the completion of activities for the tasks in the relevant WP as set out in the GA Description of the Action. WPLs were chosen based on their specific expertise and experience. They are supported by Task Leaders. The WP Leaders make WP-related decisions and prepare input for the Coordinator.

1.2.7. Data Protection Officer (DPO)

The details regarding DPO will be defined in D8.2- Data Management Plan and Ethical Monitoring Processes due in M6.

2. General operational procedures

The following sections will explain the rules and regulations the general operational procedures are based on, highlighting the workflow of organizing meetings and the voting process.

2.1. Projects meetings

2.1.1. Representation in meetings

Members of the PMB or TMB should be present or represented at any meeting. If they cannot attend a meeting, they should appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at the meeting; and who will participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

2.1.2. Organization of meetings

The chair of the relevant board shall convene meetings of that board.

Board	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	At least once a year	At any time upon request of the Technical Management Board or 1/3 of the Members of the Project Management Board
Technical Management Board	At least twice a year	At any time upon request of any Member of the Technical Management Board

Table 1: Organization of meetings overview

2.1.3. Giving notice of a meeting

The chair of the relevant board shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member of that board as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Board	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Technical Management Board	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

Table 2: Giving notice of a meeting overview

2.1.4. Preparing and sending the agenda

The chair of a board shall prepare and send each Member of that board an agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Project Management Board	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
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Technical Management Board	7 calendar days
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Table 3: Sending the agenda-timeline

2.1.5. Adding items to the agenda

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members of a board must be identified as such on the agenda. Any Member of a board may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all the other Members of that board up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below. During a meeting the Members of a board present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

Project Management Board	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Technical Management Board	2 calendar days

Table 4: Adding items to the agenda-timeline

2.1.6. Running meetings and decision making

Meetings of each board may be held by teleconference or videoconference, or other telecommunication means. Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the minutes has been accepted.

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if:

- 1) the Project Coordinator circulates to all Members of the Project Management Board a suggested decision with a deadline for responses of at least 10 calendar days after receipt by a Party; and
- 2) the decision is agreed by at least 2/3 of the Parties with voting right.

The Project Coordinator shall inform all the Parties of the outcome of the vote. A veto may be submitted up to 15 calendar days after receipt of this information. The decision will be binding after the Project Coordinator sends a notification to all Members. The Project Coordinator will keep records of the votes and make them available to the Parties on request.

2.1.7. Voting rules and quorum

Quorum of Consortium Bodies

Each board shall not deliberate and decide validly in meetings unless a quorum of two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented. If the quorum is not reached, the chair of the board shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented.

Each Member present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote. Associated Partners are excluded from certain decisions of the Project Management Board. A Party which the PMB has declared to be a Defaulting Party may not vote.

Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast.

2.1.8. Veto rights

A Party that can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of a board may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.

When the decision is included on the original agenda, a Party may only veto such a decision during the meeting.

When a decision has been taken on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a Party may veto such decision during the meeting or within 15 calendar days after receipt of the draft minutes of the meeting.

A Party that is not appointed to participate to a particular board may veto a decision within the same number of calendar days after receipt of the draft minutes of the meeting.

When a decision has been taken without a meeting a Party may veto such decision within 15 calendar days after written notice by the chairperson of the outcome of the vote.

In case of exercise of veto, the Members of the related board shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all the Parties.

A Party may neither veto decisions relating to its identification to be in breach of its obligations nor to its identification as a Defaulting Party. The Defaulting Party may not veto decisions relating to its participation and termination in the Consortium or the consequences of them.

A Party requesting to leave the Consortium may not veto decisions relating thereto.

2.1.9. Minutes of meetings

The chairperson of a board shall produce minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. He/she shall send the draft minutes to all Members within 10 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from receipt, no Member has sent an objection by written notice to the chair with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes by written notice.

The chair of meetings shall distribute the accepted minutes to all the Parties and to the Project Coordinator, who shall retain copies of them.

2.2. Progress monitoring

Besides the PMB and TMB meetings to keep up with the daily operation and development of the project there is a weekly project meeting that takes place each Thursday morning (at the time of the submission of this deliverable). This helps the Coordinator; the PM and all project members keep up with the latest updates of the project's progress.

While the project's structure is defined via the Work Packages, in order to tackle inter-WP technical work, several working groups were identified. Contributors to these working groups have dedicated ad hoc meetings to manage and coordinate their tasks. The outcomes of these meetings are communicated during the weekly project meetings.

3. Reporting

Project starting date	1th January 2024
Duration of the Project	36M
The reporting periods	Reporting Period 1. M1-M18 Reporting Period 2. M19-M36
End of first reporting period	2025.06.30.
End of second reporting period	2026.12.31.

Table 5: Reporting overview

3.1. Project reports

Interim reports will be used to collect information about the status of the project and the progress achieved by each single partner in the tasks/WPs of their responsibility, as well as the progress of the project as a whole. These reports shall include information on activities realised, results reached, usage of resources, issues (if any) arose during the period of reference and contingency plans suggested and/or agreed to solve the issues. Interim monitoring reports are useful for identifying strengths and weaknesses, and for providing the responsible people with sufficient information to make the right decisions at the right time to improve the quality of the results.

The following interim reports are expected to be prepared during the project: at M6, M12, M24, M30. Since the project must prepare Periodic Reports in M18 and M36 there is no need for an additional Interim Report. Template and reminder will be sent at least 5 weeks before deadline by the Coordinator.

Throughout the project's lifetime two **Periodic Reports** must be produced. The Reporting Periods are set out in the GA and are due at M18 and M36. These reports include a technical and financial part and must be prepared using the template available in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool. The financial part includes the financial statement containing the lump sum contributions indicated in the GA's Annex 2 for WPs that were completed during the Reporting Period.

The Coordinator will send a reminder message to the partners 30 days prior to the end of each reporting period and describes in detail what is expected from the partners during the compilation of the report. Then the Coordinator ensures that the report is produced adequately and in high quality and submits it on the portal before the deadline.

3.2. Project deliverables

Swarmchestrato must produce 14 deliverables over 36 months. (The list of the deliverables is included in the DoA (Part A) of the Grant Agreement.) The responsible partners, either Beneficiaries or Associated Partners (Lead Parties) for each deliverable are defined in the Description of the Action. Each deliverable is assigned two internal reviewers upon the proposal of the WP Leader. The leader of the deliverable must send the document for internal review 30 days prior to the delivery date. The deadline for the final delivery is the last day of the month the deliverable is due. WP members contribute to the compilation of the deliverable, but the coordination is within the responsibility of the dedicated partner.

WP Leaders support the Coordinator in ensuring that the deliverables are produced in high quality and in a timely manner. Furthermore, quality assurance is also assisted by the PM. Should any issues arise during the process the PO is notified accordingly.

4. Collaboration in Swarmchestrator

The following section will discuss the tools that the project uses for effective collaboration, meaning internal and external communication and event organization.

4.1. Communication with the Commission

All communication between the Consortium and the EC will be carried out via the Participant Portal. Each partner can grant and revoke access for members of his/her own organization in the Participant Portal. Access to the Participant Portal may have IPR or data protection implications, because sensitive data is available there.

The Coordinator is responsible for an efficient communication between the Consortium and the EC. Being the single point of contact, any communication of the partners with the EC shall pass through the Coordinator. This means that the partners shall not directly contact the EC officers for questions regarding the project.

4.2. Internal communication

Parties shall provide updated information regarding administrative data such as address to which send paper documentation (i.e. countersigned version of the CA), person of contacts, banking information form, changes in legal structure (change of ownership, change of name, etc.).

4.2.1. E-mail lists

To allow an effective communication among people involved in the project, the Coordinator set up and operates a mailing list (swarmchestrator@sztaki.hu). As the project evolves, further mailing lists shall be created separated per function in the organisation, involvement in the project, etc.

The contacts for the mailing list are continuously updated by the Coordinator, after receiving request for update by the project partners. The latest version of a detailed list of contacts is available in the project's Nextcloud instance.

4.3. External communication

4.3.1. Project website

The project's primary online presence is via the project website that is currently being populated. The domain name is www.swarmchestrator.eu and just the project also owns the www.swarmchestrator.com domain. An automated redirect is embedded here, so should anyone end up here by accident looking for the project's website will be pointed to the official one.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the website (under construction)

4.3.2. Social media presence

With the intention of reaching multiple target audiences the project also maintains social media accounts on LinkedIn and X.

Account name:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/swarmchestrato/>

Account name:

@swarmchestrato

Table 6: Overview of Swarmchestrato's social media outlets

The detailed description of the project's communication strategy will be included in Deliverable 8.1 that is due M6.

4.3.3. Tools supporting meeting and event organization

For project/task/WP or working group-level meetings, the project will use **Zoom**, since the coordinator has a subscription. Smaller, ad-hoc meetings can use other tools if they decide to.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the first online Zoom meeting

Doodle helps to decide on meeting slots and arrange voting within the project Consortium.

Indico supports event organization by providing a dedicated page for each event the project is hosting virtually or face to face. It is a one-stop-shop for handling registration, sharing the agenda, and distributing the presentations and other materials. On top of it all it serves as an inventory for all the events organized by the project. The platform is hosted and operated by the Coordinator.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the first online Swarmchestrato event's Indico page

4.3.4. Workspace-shared folder

The Coordinator hosts a Nextcloud instance where we created a project space for Swarmchestrator partners. All project-related documents are uploaded and accessible here. Nextcloud incorporates collaborative features then enhances cooperation between the partners.

Figure 4: Nextcloud screenshot